

Event Abstract

Perceptions of Libyan Community Pharmacists on Pharmacovigilance Activities

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Background: Pharmacovigilance has not progressed well in Libya and its practice and concept still in its early stage. There is a paucity of information on the knowledge and perceptions of Libyan pharmacists on pharmacovigilance activities. The aim of this study was to determine the knowledge, perception, and practice of pharmacovigilance among community pharmacists in Tripoli, Libya.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional questionnaire-based study conducted among pharmacists in different community pharmacies in Tripoli city. A total of 405 participants completed the self-administered and validated questionnaire during the period from October 2019 to February 2020.

Results: There was poor knowledge of pharmacovigilance and ADRs reporting among surveyed pharmacists. However, pharmacists had satisfied perception rate. Out of the 408, 28.9% and 14.7% of respondents answered correctly for the definition of pharmacovigilance and knew that there is center for pharmacovigilance in Libya, respectively. Nevertheless, the majority of pharmacists (77.2%) stated that pharmacovigilance needs to be included in curriculum, and 73% confirmed that they will practice pharmacovigilance if trained.

Conclusion: Outcomes of this study point us towards a critical part of drug safety that is lack of knowledge toward pharmacovigilance and ADRs reporting in community pharmacists. The deficiency of knowledge also reflects on their poor ADRs reporting practice. Integration of pharmacovigilance concepts in education curriculum, training of pharmacists in ADRs reporting is very crucial in achieving better drug safety.

Keywords: Pharmacovigilance, Adverse Drug Reactions, Pharmacists, Knowledge.

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